

The First Law of Thermodynamics and the Abstraction to a Lack of Information in a Deterministic System Part 2

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In Part 1, we considered the deterministic situation of a single particle with momentum p bouncing elastically in a box of length l and compared it to the first law of thermodynamics with $E = p^2/2m$ and $Pdl = TdS$ where $T = p^2/m$. This approach leads to the presence of a TdS term with S being given by the Sackur-Tetrode equation. Here we argue that the reason that TdS appears is due to the forced notion of pressure as the force which changes l to $l+dl$. Pressure assumes a steady stream of particles continuously impinging on a wall and so links Fdt from impulse to the flux p of the particles. For a single particle, one is then imagining a steady stream of such particles with a flux p/m . Physically, however, there is no real pressure in the picture as one does not have a steady stream scenario, but rather an impulse hit at periodic times. It is only by forcing the notion of pressure, i.e. using an ensemble, and using this to compute work $-Pdl$ that one creates an unusual kind of work which is not equal to $dE = dp^2/2m$ as in Newtonian mechanics. This then forces one to use the notion of entropy in order to have a second term TdS ($T = p^2/m$) to ensure that $dE = dp^2/2m$. Thus, it seems that the averaged notion of force associated with pressure P and work $-Pdl$ leads to the notion of entropy by imposing an ensemble average force which does not really hold for a single deterministic case. Physically, one might argue that if a nonelastic interaction occurs at the wall, then $d(p^2/2m) = Fdl$ without any notion of pressure.

A Single Particle in a 1-Dimensional Box

In Newtonian mechanics, it is possible to have the deterministic scenario of a single particle with momentum p bouncing back and forth elastically in a box. This is a deterministic problem. For such a particle:

$$dE = dp^2/2m \quad ((1))$$

This means that if the collision at the wall is nonelastic, then:

$$dE = dp^2/2m = \text{Force } dl \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, no first law of thermodynamics appears and no notion of pressure either.

It is, however, possible to create an equation which has the appearance of the first law of thermodynamics as done in references (1) and (2) listed in Part 1. The fundamental aspect of such an approach seems to be based on the notion of pressure.

If a Newtonian particle hits the wall in an inelastic way, then:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((3))$$

There is no notion of pressure in ((3)) and so we argue that ((3)) does not directly lead to the first law of thermodynamics. It is only if one introduces the notion of pressure that one has:

$$-P dl = dwork \quad ((4))$$

The notion on pressure, however, is based on the idea that:

$$dp = 2p \text{ or at least } p \text{ with a flux of } p/m \quad ((5))$$

Thus, there is a specific force dt time in ((3)) which does not occur for a single particle. As a result, it seems that one creates an ensemble of single particles which then physically resemble a steady stream (which is not the physical scenario of a single particle). It is this steady stream which creates the pressure force:

$$P l = nRT \text{ where } nR=1 \text{ and } T = pp/m \text{ so that } E = \frac{1}{2} T \text{ for one dimension} \quad ((6))$$

This gives rise to a work term:

$$-pp/m \, 1/l \, dl \quad ((7))$$

((7)), however, only applies to a steady stream picture and not the single particle case. The steady stream work ((7)) then forces one to have a second term TdS to ensure that one has:

$$dE = dpp/2m \quad ((8))$$

TdS then leads to an S which follows the Sackur-Tetrode form as discussed in Part 1.

The only way that one may even consider the notion of pressure is by creating an ensemble and arguing that it is equivalent to a steady stream. For a single particle, the interaction can only occur at the wall and

$$dE = dpp/2m = F dl \quad ((8))$$

Force is not necessarily linked to pressure which is associated with $dp = 2p$ or p . For an inelastic interaction force is whatever it is. Given a deterministic system, the first law of thermodynamics arises if one imposes an unusual pressure-force for a single particle. Physically this should not exist, but if one takes the notion of average too seriously (as in this deterministic case of a single particle), this notion leads to a steady stream probability which does not really exist in reality, we argue.

Thus, one may use statistical abstraction on a deterministic system, but it seems that one is actually changing the physics of the system by taking the notion of the average too literally. In particular, one imagines a pressure at all instants of time on the walls which is not the case.

Stochasticity

We have considered the case of a deterministic single particle elastically bouncing back and forth in a 1-dimensional box of size l . If one really has determinism, it seems there is no reason to create the notion of an ensemble average. Even if one does not know $x(t)$, there is a single particle and its nonelastic hit on the wall should follow $dE = dp^2/2m = Fdl$. It is only if one had a set of single particles with different p values that creating a priori some kind of ensemble might make sense. Even in such a case, $dpp/2m = Fdx$ for each case, but given that one cannot keep track of all of the p values and F values, one might resort to a pressure. For a single deterministic system, it seems that an ensemble average takes the notion of average too seriously as physically the notion of pressure would only hold if one had time resolution of the order of l/v with $v=p/m$. Creating the notion of pressure based on such bad resolution and then computing work based on such a pressure becomes a major approximation which seems to be quite far away from the physical situation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is possible to take the notion of average too seriously in a deterministic problem, it seems. If one has a single particle bouncing back and forth in a 1-dimensional box of length l , then there is really no sense of pressure as there are discrete hits at each wall. One may say that on average there is a pressure, but physically that is not what one would measure. In the case of an inelastic hit at a wall: $dE = dp^2/2m = F dl$ where Force would not necessarily have anything to do with a pressure. If one takes the average notion too seriously, one thinks of a steady stream and a pressure at the wall at all times and this leads to a work calculation $-P dl$ where $P l = nR T$ with $T=pp/m$ so that $E=.5 T$ and $nR=1$. This unusual work (based on a steady stream average picture which does not really exist) then forces one to introduce a TdS term, with S given by the Sackur-Tetrode equation in order to ensure that $dE = dp^2/2m$. As a result, one may see that an abstraction of a deterministic system may lead to a statistical description which may not really exist physically for a single system. It might only have applicability over an ensemble.